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The use of CytoSorb therapy in COVID-19 cytokine storm

Domina Petric, MD

ABSTRACT

The CytoSorb whole blood adsorber is a CE approved medical device for the extracorporeal removal of cytokines. The aim is to reduce excessive cytokine levels and other inflammatory mediators, while maintaining the physiological immune response. It is documented in the literature that critically ill patients with COVID-19 had the increased levels of many pro-inflammatory cytokines. Based on the up to date published clinical experiences on the use of CytoSorb therapy for COVID-19 patients developing cytokine storm, CytoSorb cartridge provided a safe rescue therapy in life-threatening COVID-19.

INTRODUCTION

The CytoSorb whole blood adsorber is a CE approved medical device for the extracorporeal removal of cytokines. The aim is to reduce excessive cytokine levels and other inflammatory mediators, while maintaining the physiological immune response. Also, the removal of elevated levels of bilirubin and myoglobin by the adsorber has been confirmed. It has also been observed that other hydrophobic

substances of medium molecular size, such as free hemoglobin and various bacterial enterotoxins, can also be effectively removed¹.

CYTOSORB THERAPY IN COVID-19 CYTOKINE STORM

Based on international guideline recommendations² CytoSorb therapy should be considered, if one or more of the following criteria are met:

1. Pronounced vasoplegia (NE > 0.3 µg/kg/min, lactate ↑) without response to standard therapy (start of CytoSorb within the first 6 to maximum 24 hours)
2. Moderate ARDS
3. Indication for ECMO/ECLS therapy
4. AKI (acute kidney injury) III with start of CVVH (CRRT)
5. H-Score suggesting diagnosis of secondary HLH (hemophagocytic lymphohistiocytosis)

CytoSorb is to be employed as an adjunctive therapy to lower cytokine storm, not as a primary therapy removing SARS-CoV-2. Due to its concentration dependency CytoSorb does not completely eliminate cytokines from the body, but rebalances the immune system to more physiologic levels.

CytoSorb can be integrated into renal replacement therapy circuits or as a bypass in ECMO systems. Alternatively, use in stand-alone hemoperfusion is possible.

Treatment duration and indication for exchange of adsorber depends on the clinical course. The maximum treatment time per adsorber is 24 hours.

Recommended blood flow rate is 150-700 ml/min with a minimal flow of 100 ml/min. Ideal flow rates using CRRT with systemic heparin anticoagulation seem to be 200-250 ml/min. Flow rates for regional citrate anti-coagulation are normally lower and should adhere to the corresponding protocols. Higher flow rates generally result in higher detoxification.

Rizvi and coworkers³ published a case report that demonstrates the utility of CytoSorb therapy in a critically ill COVID-19 patient who survived the

cytokine storm after receiving the cytokine filter via continuous renal replacement therapy bridging him to further definitive therapy. Furthermore, authors concluded that the Cytosorbents® cytokine filter is a potential treatment methodology aimed at reducing the cytokine storm, thus serving as a bridge for therapy in the acutely ill patients infected with COVID-19.

According to recent findings, the characteristics of hemophagocytic lymphohistiocytosis are similar to the critically ill patients with COVID-19. Therefore, these two diseases may have a common treatment. The cytokines observed in the critically ill patients with COVID-19 are increased interleukin (IL)-1, IL-2, IL-6, IL-7, granulocyte colony-stimulating factor, interferon- γ inducible protein 10, monocyte chemoattractant protein 1, macrophage inflammatory protein 1- α , and tumor necrosis factor- α ⁴⁻⁷.

A meta-analysis study suggested a cutoff of more than 55 pg/mL of IL-6 for identifying patients at high risk of severe COVID-19. More than 80 pg/mL of IL-6 can be used for identifying patients at high risk of mortality⁸.

Based on these findings, CytoSorb therapy should be effective in treating critically ill patients with COVID-19 with ARDS and

hyperinflammatory syndrome by removing inflammatory factors from the plasma⁹.

Alharthy and coworkers investigated continuous renal replacement therapy (CRRT) with CytoSorb cartridge for patients with life-threatening COVID-19 plus acute kidney injury (AKI), sepsis, acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), and cytokine release syndrome (CRS). Of 492 COVID-19 patients admitted to intensive care unit (ICU), 50 had AKI necessitating CRRT (10.16%) and were enrolled in the study. Upon ICU admission, all had AKI, ARDS, septic shock, and CRS. In addition to CRRT with CytoSorb, all received ARDS-net ventilation, prone positioning, plus empiric ribavirin, interferon beta-1b, antibiotics, hydrocortisone, and prophylactic anticoagulation. Authors retrospectively analyzed inflammatory biomarkers, oxygenation, organ function, duration of mechanical ventilation, ICU length-of-stay, and mortality on day-28 post-ICU admission. Patients were 49.64 ± 8.90 years old (78% male) with body mass index of 26.70 ± 2.76 kg/m². On ICU admission, mean Acute Physiology and Chronic Health Evaluation (APACHE) II was 22.52 ± 1.1 . Sequential Organ Function Assessment (SOFA) score was 9.36 ± 2.068 and the ratio of partial arterial pressure of oxygen to fractional

inspired concentration of oxygen ($\text{PaO}_2/\text{FiO}_2$) was 117.46 ± 36.92 . Duration of mechanical ventilation was 17.38 ± 7.39 days, ICU length-of-stay was 20.70 ± 8.83 days, and mortality 28 days post-ICU admission was 30%. Non-survivors had higher levels of inflammatory biomarkers, and more unresolved shock, ARDS, AKI, and pulmonary emboli (8% vs. 4%, $P < .05$) compared to survivors. After 2 ± 1 CRRT sessions with CytoSorb, survivors had decreased SOFA scores, lactate dehydrogenase, ferritin, D-dimers, C-reactive protein, and interleukin-6; and increased $\text{PaO}_2/\text{FiO}_2$ ratios, and lymphocyte counts (all $P < .05$). Receiver-operator-curve analysis showed that post-therapy values of interleukin-6 (cutoff point >620 pg/mL) predicted in-hospital mortality for critically ill COVID-19 patients (area-under-the-curve: 0.87, 95% CI: 0.81-0.93; $P = .001$). No side effects of therapy were recorded. In this retrospective case-series, CRRT with the CytoSorb cartridge provided a safe rescue therapy in life-threatening COVID-19 with associated AKI, ARDS, sepsis, and hyperinflammation¹⁰.

CONCLUSION

The CytoSorb whole blood adsorber is a CE approved medical device for the extracorporeal removal of cytokines. The aim is to reduce excessive cytokine levels and other inflammatory mediators, while maintaining the physiological immune response.

The characteristics of hemophagocytic lymphohistiocytosis are similar to the critically ill patients with COVID-19. The cytokines observed in the critically ill patients with COVID-19 are increased interleukin (IL)-1, IL-2, IL-6, IL-7, granulocyte colony-stimulating factor, interferon- γ inducible protein 10, monocyte chemoattractant protein 1, macrophage inflammatory protein 1- α , and tumor necrosis factor- α .

Based on the up to date published clinical experiences on the use of CytoSorb therapy for COVID-19 patients developing cytokine storm, CytoSorb cartridge provided a safe rescue therapy in life-threatening COVID-19.

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